

VALVE TYPE SELECTION

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ABSTRACT

This clause considers the factors involved in valve selection and provides a means of determining the most suitable type (or types) of block and check valves for a particular application, given basic information about the service conditions.

a. A selection chart (refer to 1) in its spreadsheet form, that speedily identifies appropriate valve types for a given set of selected operating conditions.

b. Valve manufacturers should be asked to confirm suitability of a particular valve type for the required service, and for the more complicated cases selection should be reviewed by a BP responsible engineer.

c. New projects should create a project specific valve type selection chart or matrix that lists:

1. Principal services.
2. Service conditions.
3. Appropriate valve type (including trim).

Keywords: valve, service, fluid, steam, lube oil, diesel oil, methanol.

Valve type selection should take account of:

- a. Required function.
- b. Service conditions.
- c. Fluid type and condition.
- d. Fluid characteristics.
- e. Frequency of operation.
- f. Isolation requirements.
- g. Maintenance requirements.
- h. Environmental considerations.
- i. Past experience in comparable conditions.
- j. Weight and size.
- k. Cost.

Required function Valve basic function should be identified as either required for isolation (block) or for prevention of flow reversal (check). The characteristics of different isolation and check valve types are described in next.

İşin məqsədi. Service conditions If the service is defined as either hazardous process or hazardous utilities, the following should not be used: a. Cast iron valves. b. Copper alloy valves. c. Plastic valves. Pressure and temperature (maximum and minimum) have a major effect on valve choice. Valves containing elastomer or polymer parts are not normally useable above 200°C (390°F), and some valve types are not useful at high pressure.

Fluid type and its particular condition should be identified, such as liquid, dry or wet gas, multiphase, abrasive slurry, etc. The nature of the working fluid (and, if appropriate, test and dosing fluids) (i.e., whether it is a liquid, gas, multiphase, slurry, etc., and whether it is clean or dirty) affect valve type selection. Dry gas and solvents, such as methanol and methylated spirit, tend to remove all traces of lubricant from valve parts such that, if operated "dry", operating forces might need to be two or three times those required in the "lubricated" condition. Steam service usually excludes valves with polymer or elastomer seals, etc. Abrasive particles, such as catalyst fines or sand, cause wear in the moving parts of valves and, sometimes, erosion of parts in the flow path. Only valve types having

very hard (or, sometimes, very soft) trim materials are useful.

Fluid characteristics. Particular fluid characteristics shall be identified, such as clean or dirty, viscous, solidifying, searching, hazardous, corrosive, sour, vacuum, high or low temperature cryogenic, etc. Very viscous fluids and solidifying fluids often require valves to have trace heating or steam jackets. Solidifying product can also necessitate a steam purge facility. Scaling service provides a most difficult environment for valves and designs that use self cleaning features (such as a scraping action) are usually best suited.

Selection of valves that are frequently operated should take into account the fact that:

a. Shutoff capability is likely to deteriorate.

b. The fitting of another valve (normally open) in series might be necessary to ensure adequate isolation.

Most isolation valves are not operated frequently, although some might be (valves on regenerative processes, diverter service, etc.). If operation is infrequent, there is likely to be an increase in the required operating force with time. Isolation requirements a. Very few valve types can maintain completely tight shutoff over a significant period of operation. This number is reduced still further if the working fluid is gas or if it contains abrasive particles. b. The facts in a. should be taken into account in selection (e.g., some valve types offer a double isolation in a single body) and system design (multiple valves, provision of adequately sized venting facilities, etc.). The need for intervention in a "live" system determines the seat leak tightness requirements for valves isolating equipment. Shutdown valves are rarely required to shut off tight and are often acceptable with a significant through seat leak rate.

Check valves isolate against gross reverse flow and rarely, if ever, shut off tight and should be assumed not to do so in process design. Maintenance requirements Appropriate access to valve and actuator for removal or maintenance in situ should be evaluated in the selection process. The location and available facilities,

etc., affect the potential for valve maintenance and therefore affect valve selection.

Environmental considerations. The required degree of control of emissions to the environment should be determined based on the nature (flammability, toxicity, and searching tendency) of the process fluid or sensitivity of the environment (e.g., marine). Valve stem seals are the most frequent source of emissions. In general, valves that have rotary quarter turn operation are inherently less prone to emissions than those with rising stems. The fewer flanged joints that a valve has, the better. Previous experience (good and bad) should be taken into account, because experience relates to comparable service conditions. Sometimes, however, local expectations are conditioned by a lack of knowledge of available alternatives. Weight and size factors should not be allowed to determine valve type if they do not represent a constraint (e.g., in new, on-shore construction). In some applications, though, it is necessary to try to minimise one or both.

Cost - Whole life cost should be evaluated, not just purchase price. Higher priced valve options frequently turn out to be less costly on this basis, particularly if unscheduled plant shutdown can be avoided. Selection charts a. GN 62-001 provides assistance with selection of block and check valve types for more common service requirements, based on the required operating conditions. b. GN 62-001 provides assistance only, and users should ascertain that service conditions are within valve manufacturer recommendations for any particular valve type. c. If a variety of valve types appear to be suitable, the user should evaluate the following:

1. Their past experience for the service.
2. Additional factors that affect valve choice, such as:

- a) Speed of operation.
- b) Availability.
- c) Factors listed in this article, that are not considered in the tables. The less onerous the service conditions, the wider the choice of possible valve types. d. If any required box in a table is blank, the valve type should be discounted from consideration. e. Further assistance can be obtained from more detailed information provided throughout this GP. f. More difficult cases should be reviewed by a BP responsible engineer. The charts assume that materials are chosen to be compatible with the working fluid, test fluids, and dosing fluids. Characteristics and condition of the process fluid shall be defined. The characteristics and condition of the process fluid are often the most significant factors in selecting the correct type of valve. For example, clean fluids generally allow a wide choice of valve types, whereas, for dirty or abrasive fluids, the choice is restricted. Hazardous (flammable, hazardous) and searching fluids require special consideration to be given to stem, body, and seat seals. Characteristics of a fluid can fit one or more categories of service. Clean service a. The term “clean service” is used to identify fluids free from solids or contaminants. b. Clean fluids should be assumed to include: 1. Instrument air. 2. Nitrogen and other manufactured gases. 3. Potable and demineralised water. 4. Steam. 5. Lube oil. 6. Diesel oil.

7. Methanol. 8. Most dosing and injection chemicals. c. Valves for fluids, such as oxygen, hydrogen peroxide, and sometimes treated water or lube oil, shall require special attention to cleanliness of the valve. d. Valves for potable water shall comply with local regulations. e. Valves used in ballasting and other hull type equipment of floating structures can be under jurisdiction of local regulators such as American Bureau of Shipping and/or coastguard, with special additional requirements. f. Process fluids may be defined as clean, depending on which part of the process is being considered (e.g., dry hydrocarbon gas downstream of scrubbers and dryers). Clean services are generally less damaging to valves, resulting in long term performance and reliability. Selection from a wide range of valve types is possible for most applications, allowing greater freedom of choice. g. If the fluid service has no entrained solids or particles, attention should be given to protecting valves during construction and during flushing operations that are unlikely to be clean, as follows:

1. This protection might require the temporary replacement of valves by spool pieces.

2. Alternatively, a valve type may be selected that is suitable for dirty service.

The general term “dirty service” is used to identify fluids with suspended solids that can seriously impair the performance of valves unless the correct type is selected. Characteristics of dirty service that should be evaluated include the following:

1. Dirty service is often of major significance since many valves are very sensitive to the presence of solids.
2. Dirty service can be further classified as generally abrasive or sandy.

Valves intended for starting and stopping flow or for isolation of equipment should generally be selected to provide:

1. Low resistance to flow (LP drop) (e.g., by means of a straight through flow configuration that can also facilitate line clearing).

2. Bidirectional sealing (providing good shutoff if the flow or pressure differential is from either direction).

If flow is not necessary (e.g., isolation of instrument piping), valve types, such as needle and globe, which have a high resistance to flow may be used, as follows:

1. To provide crude flow control.
2. Not in fouling or solidifying service. The most common types of block valves include:

- Gate valves - wedge/parallel slab/parallel expanding/parallel slide.
- Ball valves - floating ball/trunnion mounted, metal/soft seats.
- Butterfly valves - double or triple offset/rubber lined.
- Plug valves - lubricated balanced/sleeved, lined/expanding/lift.
- Diaphragm valves - weir/full flow/pinch.
- Globe valves - straight/angle/Y pattern/needle/piston/stop and check.

All of these valve types have application in process or utility service.

Gate valves are used for on/off operation on hydrocarbon, general process, and utilities service for all temperature ranges. They have a straight through configuration.

Gate valve types are:

- Wedge
 - Expanding parallel (internal wedge). (Usually provided as “through conduit” that offers an uninterrupted pipe bore in the fully open position.)
 - Parallel slab. (Usually provided as “through conduit” that offers an uninterrupted pipe bore in the fully open position.)
 - Parallel slide. (Also available in “through conduit” version.)
 - Knife edge.

Extended bonnets are available (and should be specified) for cryogenic service. Gate valves should not be used:

1. In horizontal lines transporting heavy or abrasive slurries in which sediment can become trapped in

the pocket below the valve seat, preventing closure. Reverse acting through conduit and knife edged types are unaffected by this.

2. For throttling duties, as the valve is very inefficient at controlling flow. Full flow persists until the valve is 80% closed and very high velocities can be generated. Erosion of seats and gate, etc., can cause leakage.

The wedge gate valve is the most common type of gate valve. Closure is obtained by driving a taper wedge gate between two similar taper wedge seats. Steel wedge gate valves are classified by wedge type: plain solid wedge, flexible solid wedge (having a groove cut around the circumference, refer to Figure 6), and split wedge (two separate halves). A flexible solid wedge can more easily accommodate misaligned seats and minimise galling of sealing surfaces, but the degree of flexibility is extremely limited in small sizes. A plain solid wedge can be more difficult to grind to an accurate fit. Seats are fixed.

Fig. 1. Wedge gate valve (outside screw)

Fig 2. Wedge Gate and Parallel Gate in Gate Valve Design

Solid and flexible wedge gate valves are good general service block valves, offering a good sealing capability with LP drop. A 100% shutoff capability cannot always be relied on, however, slight leakage can occur with variations in temperature and pressure after being in service for some time. Standard steel wedge gate valves normally should be specified with the following:

1. OS&Y.
2. Rising stem.
3. Nonrising handwheel.
4. Bolted bonnet.

Valves smaller than DN 50 (NPS 2) normally should have solid wedges. Larger valves for general service normally should have flexible wedges.

Split wedges should be reserved for the following applications:

1. Steam applications in which good low differential pressure sealing is required.
2. Comparable applications in which a parallel slide valve cannot be used.

Wedge gate valves are prone to “thermal wedging” if subjected to temperature changes after closure, resulting in high “breakout” forces. In these and similar conditions, in which the valve body can deform following a change in process conditions, a split wedge type valve might be preferred. The two piece gate can adjust to changes in seat angle, thus maintaining a better seal. Breakout forces are equally high, however. The same problem could theoretically occur with solid or split wedge gate valves, but, in this case, distortion of the body at high pressure usually causes venting to occur across the seats and into the pipe.

Split wedge gate valves in liquid or condensing service that might be subject to heat (process, fire, etc.) if the valve is closed should have a means of relieving pressure built up in the body cavity. If conforming to the requirement in e. involves making the valve unidirectional, the flow direction shall be clearly marked. Services with abrasive particles or applications in

which wire drawing is possible shall have hard faced wedges and seats.

Wedge gate valves can have seating problems on dirty service due to material collecting on seats or in the body cavity of the valve but might offer a better life on service other than soft seated ball valves. Slab gate types are a better choice for such services, because the gate cleans the seat and there is less chance of solids entering body cavities. Some special rubber seated designs of wedge gates have good sealing characteristics if used on applications containing solids but have limited pressure and temperature range. Other soft seat materials can give improved shutoff capability but are usually damaged by hard particles and are not suitable for dirty service. Slab or expanding gate valves are preferred for HP gas service. A wedge gate valve does not shut off against HP gas as efficiently as a slab or expanding gate valve. If flexible or solid wedge gate valves are installed below the horizontal, the valve bonnet should have a drain. Split wedge and double disc gate valves shall be installed with the valve stem vertical, unless additional guides are provided in the valve for the particular application. It is essential to provide adequate support of the gate to avoid unacceptable stem deflection, galling, and stem packing leakage. Cast iron valves should not be used, except for underground water service in which freezing is not a possibility and piping specification permits.

Conclusions

API Std 603 allows reduced wall thickness on the grounds that the material does not corrode. If Class 150 stainless steel wedge gate valves are specified in accordance with API Std 603, the general requirements of GIS 62-011 should be met. API Std 603 valves should not be used if the specified corrosion allowance of the connecting pipe exceeds 0,7 mm (0,03 in) or for pressure ratings greater than Class 150. Gate valves greater than DN 50 (NPS 2) are normally provided with reduced (sometimes called conventional or standard) port

in accordance with the minimum diameters specified in the reference standard (e.g., ISO 15761). Full port valves might be available at increased cost and delivery. These valves are also available with extended body outlets that can be used instead of gate valve plus pipe nipple assemblies.

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